

Detrimental effects of niclosamide 250EC at preseeding in direct-seeded rice culture

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During the field evaluation of the potential low-dose metaldehyde formulation against golden apple snail (*GAS*), *Pomacea canaliculata* (Lamarck), we consistently observed that only microplots treated with niclosamide 250EC had adverse effects on the growth and establishment of direct-seeded rice (DSR). This prompted us to verify field observations under greenhouse tests at the PhilRice-Central Experiment Station in Nueva Ecija, Philippines.

Commercial synthetic molluscicides such as niclosamide 250EC and metaldehyde are used among lowland irrigated transplanted rice farmers in Asia. However, niclosamide 250EC is preferred over metaldehyde formulations because of its "quick-kill" action on GAS. Unfortunately, niclosamide 250EC is lethal to nontarget beneficial water-borne organisms such as frogs, fish, etc. Hence, in the future, it is important for rice farmers to practice ecologically sustainable GAS management options that are safe to the rice crop, their health, and their environment.

Healthy seeds of rice variety IR64 were selected using the flotation method. The seeds were soaked in dis-

tilled water for 24 h and then incubated for 1–2 d in petri dishes lined with Whatman filter paper no. 42. The trays were filled with 1-in-thick soil. Before sowing of seeds, the trays were saturated with water; 25 sprouted seeds were sown per tray ($34.3 \times 26.7 \times 11.4$ cm), in five rows, each row having five seeds. Each treatment was replicated four times, with a total of 100 seeds. Two GAS of 15 ± 1 mm were introduced per tray after sowing of seeds. All treatments were made as sprays prior to seeding. The following were the treatments: niclosamide 250EC at 6 mL, 12 mL, and 15 mL in 15 L of water. Two kinds of control were maintained that were sprayed with water. The positive control had no niclosamide 250EC treatment but two GAS. The negative control had neither niclosamide 250EC nor GAS. Water from the trays was drained after 24 h. All the experimental conditions mirrored those in DSR farmers' fields. After 10 d, data on the number of rice seeds that emerged above the soil, rice seedling shoot and root lengths, phytotoxicity, retarded/abnormal growth of rice seedlings, and snail mortality were recorded.

The most visible serious effects of niclosamide 250EC on rice seedlings were on seedling height (see table and Figs. 2–4). The seedlings had low and uneven emergence and were stunted when treated with niclosamide 250EC. Belowground effects on rice seedlings were a marked reduction in root growth and development at all concentrations of niclosamide 250EC tested as preseeding treatment (Figs. 1 and 4). In the negative control, rice seedling height and root length were the highest (see table and Fig. 1). No phytotoxicity symptoms were observed in the field or greenhouse tests. Our greenhouse results confirmed the field observations. This has important implications for the establishment of

Effect of niclosamide 250EC on the shoot growth of DSR seedlings, PhilRice-CES, 2004.

Treatment	Rice seedling height (cm) ^a (mean $\pm$ S.D.)
6 mL niclosamide in 15 L water	5.1 $\pm$ 2.1
12 mL niclosamide in 15 L water	4.5 $\pm$ 2.0
15 mL niclosamide in 15 L water	4.3 $\pm$ 2.5
Control (+) with GAS and no niclosamide	10.1 $\pm$ 3.5
Control (-) without GAS and no niclosamide	12.5 $\pm$ 3.0

^aAverage of 100 rice seedlings in each treatment.

Fig. 1. Effect of niclosamide 250EC on root length of DSR, PhilRice-CES, 2004.

Fig. 2. Effects of 15 mL of niclosamide in 15 L of water on germinating rice seedlings in direct-seeded rice.

Fig. 3. Control rice seedlings (without GAS).

Fig. 4. Rice shoot and root lengths (cm) in control (untreated) and lengths in treatment with niclosamide 250EC.

a healthy DSR crop. Once farmers establish their crops as DSR and they use niclosamide 250EC as a preseeding treatment, they will experience very poor and

uneven crop establishment. This condition would also expose seedlings to GAS damage for a much longer time. It is therefore important to share this new finding with

DSR farmers in farmer field schools since DSR is increasing in popularity in many Asian countries and in countries where GAS has also become invasive.